

9th International Conference on Natural Language Processing (NLP 2020)

November 21~22, 2020, Zurich, Switzerland

<https://cst2020.org/nlp/index.html>

Call for Papers

9th International Conference on Natural Language Processing (NLP 2020) is a programmed approach to analyze text that is based on both a set of theories and a set of technologies. This forum aims to bring together researchers who have designed and build software that will analyze, understand, and generate languages that humans use naturally to address computers.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the Conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of Natural Language Computing in theoretical and practical aspects.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Algorithms and Data Structures
- Phonology, Morphology
- Chunking/Shallow Parsing
- Parsing/Grammatical Formalisms
- Semantic Processing
- Lexical Semantics
- Ontology
- Linguistic Resources
- Statistical and Knowledge based methods
- POS tagging
- Discourse
- Paraphrasing/Entailment/Generation
- Machine Translation
- Information Retrieval
- Text Mining
- Information Extraction
- Question Answering
- Dialog Systems
- Spoken Language Processing
- Speech Recognition and Synthesis

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **August 22, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **NLP 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journal.

- [International Journal on Computational Science & Applications \(IJCSA\)](#)
- [International Journal on Natural Language Computing \(IJNLC\)](#)
- [International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology \(IJWesT\)](#)

Important Dates

Second Batch : (Submissions after July 26, 2020)

- **Submission Deadline : August 22, 2020**
- Authors Notification : October 05, 2020
- Registration & camera - Ready Paper Due: October 13, 2020

Contact Us:

Here's where you can reach us : nlp@cst2020.org (or) nlp.conf@yahoo.com

Paper Submission URL: <https://cst2020.org/submission/index.php>